

Performance of top new plant type breeding lines of very early, early, and medium maturity groups, RARS, Bilaspur, India, 1996 wet season (WS) and dry season (DS).

Entry	Days to maturity		Plant height (cm)		Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)		Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	WS	DS
<i>Very early</i>											
NPT57K-3-6	107	137	114	85	6.7	8.7	163	207	25.1	6.4	7.7
MW10 (check)	105	138	92	79	9.3	10.0	111	121	22.7	5.2	5.6
<i>Early</i>											
NPT63K-1-20	118	143	107	86	6.7	7.3	205	260	28.2	7.4	8.2
IR36 (check)	116	142	82	72	10.0	11.0	126	139	22.8	5.7	7.2
<i>Medium</i>											
NPT63K-12-51	127	152	117	100	9.3	9.3	228	271	28.6	9.2	9.9
Kranti	128	146	106	86	11.3	11.3	129	164	28.1	6.5	7.5
LSD (0.05)	–	–	8.6	6.5	2.0	2.3	40.4	46.1	–	1.5	1.6

VL Dhan 61, a new rice variety for the northwestern Himalayan region

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A new rice variety, VL Dhan 61, was released by the Central Varietal Release Committee in 1997 for cultivation under irrigated transplanted conditions of hilly and valley areas (up to 1,150 m) of Uttar Pradesh and Himachal Pradesh. VL Dhan 61 was developed to combine high yield and blast resistance from the cross Jaya/Ta-poo-cho-z, using the pedigree method. Eighty-two desirable plants were selected in the F₂ generation in 1986. Further selection was made until uniformity was achieved.

VL Dhan (IET13485) was tested in the 1992-95 All-India Coordinated Trials at different hill sites. It yielded an average of 4.9 t ha⁻¹—16% higher than zonal check Himdhan, 22% higher than the state/local check, and 6% higher than the high-yielding test genotype (Table 1). It is a nonlodging, semitall (110 cm) variety with 130-135 d duration. It has compact, well-exserted long panicles with good spikelet fertility and long bold grains (length/breadth, 2.65). It has also shown resistance to/tolerance for prevailing biotic stresses (leaf and neck blast, stem borer) and tolerance for abiotic constraints (low temperature) (Table 2).

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of VL Dhan 61, All-India Coordinated Trials, hill zone, 1992-95.

Genotype	1992	1993	1994	1995	Mean	Gain (%)
VL Dhan 61 (IET13485)	4.8	3.6	5.0	6.2	4.9	–
Himdhan (zonal check)	4.2	3.2	2.7	4.8	4.2	16
State check	3.7	2.9	4.1	5.3	4.0	22
VL 89-1167 (IET13483)	4.1	3.2	4.8	5.6	4.4	11
VL 89-1177 (IET13484)	4.6	3.4	5.0	5.5	5.6	6

Table 2. Comparison of newly released variety VL Dhan 61 with its parents.

Character	VL Dhan 61	Parents	
		Jaya	Ta-poo-cho-z
Days to 50% flowering	103–105	100	109
Days to maturity	130–135	131	140
Plant height (cm)	110	85	90
Panicle type	Compact	Compact	Compact
Panicle length (cm)	25.5	25.2	22.0
Awn	Tip awned	Awnless	Awn
Panicle exertion	Well	Well	Well
Threshability	Easy	Moderate	Hard
1,000-grain weight (g)	23.4	25.0	23.0
Milling (%)	65.8	74.0	60.3
Kernel length (mm)	6.68	6.27	5.14
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.52	2.54	2.69
L/B (length/breadth)	2.65	2.47	1.91
Grain shape	Long bold	Long bold	Short bold
Alkali digestion value	5.2	7.0	–
Disease and insect score (0–9 score) ^a			
Leaf blast	4	–	2
Neck blast	3	5	3
False smut	3	–	–
Stem borer	3	–	–
Leaffolder	5	–	–

^aMaximum score recorded using Standard evaluation system for rice.